

IMPACT OF ONLINE TRAINING SYSTEM ON WORKING EFFICIENCY IN INDIAN INDUSTRIES

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ABSTRACT

Training and development describes the formal, ongoing efforts that are made within organizations to improve the performance and self-fulfillment of their employees through a variety of educational methods and programs. In the modern workplace, these efforts have taken on a broad range of applications—from instruction in highly specific job skills to long-term professional development. In recent years, training and development has emerged as a formal business function, an integral element of strategy, and a recognized profession with distinct theories and methodologies. More and more companies of all sizes have embraced "continual learning" and other aspects of training and development as a means of promoting employee growth and acquiring a highly skilled work force.

Key-Words: AR, VR, MR, FMCG, BPO.

Introduction:

8 Top eLearning Trends For 2019:

Let's look at the top eLearning trends for 2019 that will become stronger as we move forward:

1. Adaptive Learning Going To the Next Level

In my last year article on eLearning trends for 2018, I had predicted that adaptive learning will become stronger with greater adoption. It seems to head that way, as many new players are emerging. Adaptive learning, supported by confidence-based assessments and strong analytics and measurement of training effectiveness, is taking learning to the next level.

Very soon, in 2019, adaptive learning will make further strides in the eLearning market space. Organizations and learners will benefit as organizations ensure that there are better competition rates, and learners will enjoy the learning process as they get to see only that content that is personalized to them. Using effective assessments, learners can skip the content that they are completely confident about.

LMSs are slowly gearing up to compete with platforms that are offering adaptive learning. Hence it will be an important and interesting trend to watch out for in the coming year. My gut

feeling is, adaptive learning is here to stay and the experimentation phase is over, and it will all about action in 2019.

2. Micro learning

Micro learning was a strong trend in 2018. I have seen that organizations are increasingly looking at micro learning as an important solution. It is a great method of implementing learning in small chunks that are objective driven and can be easily and quickly deployed within organizations.

Organizations that are looking to take advantage of micro learning will continue to benefit from this interesting and innovative mode of learning.

Learners benefit too as they get through the modules quickly and can repeat the learning many times as well. Retention is better, and they are less fussy about going through a boring hour-long module.

Micro learning can be implemented as videos, small games, quizzes, and info graphics.

The great advantage of micro learning is that it can be implemented on any device. I feel micro learning will continue to be a strong trend in the year 2019 and beyond.

3. Artificial Intelligence and Learner Assistance

Artificial Intelligence assistance has picked up in the eLearning space. Organizations are now offering innovative solutions where bots are able to guide learners both on the learning path, as well as during the courses.

Artificial Intelligence will be used to predict learner behavior, as well as help personalize the learning. Based on the modules that were taken by learners and the difficulties or challenges faced, better personalization will be brought about. Voice-guided bots will also help learners to search for key content in modules. As I see it, organizations will be implementing newer methods of Artificial Intelligence support for their learners in both the learning process and during the moment of need. An example of this could be an intelligent chatbot that can act as support for technical queries.

Added to the mix is the use of robots for helping kids and people with special needs to learn new skills, and help them in the moment of need.

My take is that Artificial Intelligence will continue to be a very strong trend, and that it is something that will change the learning landscape in 2019 and beyond.

4. Gamification and Game-Based Learning

Gamification and game-based learning were strong trends in 2018. Organizations are increasingly looking at investing in game-based learning to empower and engage their learners better. It has been observed that gamification has improved retention rates and better application of the subject matter learned at work.

Organizations will look to implement more game-based solutions, as they see them as value adders for the organization-wide learning. Games that are well thought out, well designed and address the needs of learners engage them effectively. It has been proven through numerous implementations that games help in releasing happy hormones, such as dopamine and serotonin.

A learning organization is one that takes advantage of game-based learning.

In my opinion, game-based learning is here to stay, and will continue to be a strong trend in the year 2019 and beyond.

5. AR/VR/MR

Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality are both growing rapidly as important modes of implementing learning content. It has been observed that K-12 has adopted Augmented Reality in a rapid way to teach various subjects, such as Science and Math.

The great thing about Augmented Reality is that it can augment the existing content through interesting overlays of graphics and images that can pop out and thrill the learners. More than the thrill, it is the experience itself that helps learners connect to the content better.

Virtual Reality continues to grow as it is used in teaching various safety-related procedures. Organizations are now looking at Virtual Reality as an important solution, as eLearning companies use effective Instructional Design strategies to enhance the VR experience. Using a mixture of 360-degree photographs, interactions, and many more elements, VR is becoming a useful experience. Organizations are also investing in cognitive learning products that are augmented by VR especially for children and people with special needs.

Added to AR and VR is the exciting new modality called Mixed Reality or MR. Already big players are making investments in MR which combines AR and VR to a great effect.

Organizations will continue to take advantage of this interesting trend in the year 2019 and beyond.

6. Video-Based Learning

Videos are one of the hottest modes of training right now. The popularity of video-based sites like YouTube has forced organizations to adopt more videos into their training. Be it Instructor-Led Training that is interspersed with anecdotal or contextual videos, or eLearning where videos play an integral part in disseminating information, videos are here to stay.

The focus is on decreasing the load time and the size of videos using various tools. Video-based learning will continue to grow and will be an important trend to watch out for in the year 2019 and beyond.

7. Social Learning

Social learning involves collaboration between individuals at the workplace through various modes, such as forums, informal chat sessions, sharing sessions, and learning circles. Social learning has picked up in the last few years thanks to the emphasis on building a learning organization. As more collaborative tools are developed, social learning will continue to grow and leave an impact in the year 2019 and beyond.

8. Content Curation

Content curation has found a lot of support from the learning community and professionals in 2018. What will the year 2019 hold for this wonderful method of curating information and providing the learners with just-in-time information? I feel LMSs will continue to grow and offer content curation as an important method of sharing information, and provide the right experience to the learners. I see that content curation will continue to be a strong trend in the year 2019 and beyond.

NEED FOR TRAINING:

As Price has observed, a training need exists when there is a gap between the present performance of an employee or group of employees, and the desired performance. Growing business performance is a journey, not an end. The success of business operations depends upon the ups and downs of the employee performances. Hence, the HR managers started looking for the methods to boost the performance and efficiency of its workforce to carry out the work today, and to train them for meeting tomorrow's goals. Training programs were developed many years ago, but now-a-days, it has become a crucial factor in companies with certain objectives in mind. Training and development practices should boost up performance and develop the skills, knowledge and expertise of the employees.

The vital objective of training is to build-up right ability and capability in the labor force so that they can perform to meet the needs, wants and expected returns of the employers.

The need for Training may generally arise for the following-

- To improve the efficiency of employees
- To reduce wastage of time and money,
- To have quality output,
- To bring down supervision,
- To have preventive maintenance,
- To achieve optimum performance,
- To boost morale of employees,
- To prepare workforce for future challenging work,
- To reduce absenteeism,
- To bring down the grievances,
- To build career by personal growth,

TRAINING OBJECTIVES

According to Saiyadain, the objectives of training differ according to the employees belonging to different level of organizations. The basic objective of training, however, is to establish a match between man and his job. This training is designated to improve the knowledge, skills and attitude and thus, equip the individual to be more effective in his present job or prepare him for future assignment. However individual's growth should not be taken as an end. From this point of view of an organization, individual's growth is a means to organizational effectiveness. The principal objective of training and development division is to make sure the availability of a skilled and willing workforce to an organization. In addition to that, there are four other objectives: Individual, Organizational, Functional, and Societal.

Individual Objectives –

They help employees in achieving their personal goals, which in turn, enhances the individual contribution to an organization.

Organizational Objectives –

They assist the organization with its primary objective by bringing individual effectiveness.

Functional Objectives –

They maintain the department's contribution at a level suitable to the organization's needs.

Societal Objectives –

They ensure that an organization is ethically and socially responsible to the needs and challenges of the society.

Following can be briefly summarized as training objectives.

- a) To create constant awareness in the minds of all sections of employees of the mission of the industry, its objective and goals.
- b) To encourage self-development to achieve organization goals with a sense of belonging and commitment to organization and thereby ensuring development of a proper work ethics in the Industry and fostering of team spirit.
- c) To identify the training needs of the entire personnel in industry in keeping with the corporate plans and in consultation with the user departments.
- d) To impart knowledge and skills necessary for performing the job efficiently and effectively and to keep the employees to acquire necessary conceptual, technical, human and managerial skills in the areas of decision-making and problem-solving.
- e) To make available in adequate number sufficiently trained manpower to meet the diverse needs of a rapidly growing industry.
- f) To organize special training programs to improve employment opportunities as well as career prospects of persons belonging to SC/ST, minorities, handicapped, ex-servicemen, etc.
- g) To organize training activities as aids to:
 - Career Planning and growth,
 - Succession planning.
- h) To educate and equip the employees to respond to the expectations of customers, and to accept responsibilities to attain a sense of achievement.
- i) To achieve effectiveness of training through tapping the in-house training facilities as well as sources available externally in a balanced manner so as to develop internal faculty support at all levels and disciplines.
- j) To promote research and development activities and to establish linkages with the operational front.

Training and Development in Retail-FMCG Sector

Retail/FMCG Sector is the most booming sector in the Indian economy and is expected to reach US\$ 175-200 billion by 2016. With this rapid expansion and coming up of major players in the sector, the need of human resource development has increased. Lack of skilled workers is the major factor that is holding back the retail sector for high growth. The sector is facing the severe

shortage of trainers. Also, the current education system is not sufficiently prepared to address the new processes, according to the industry majors.

Training Programs in Retail/FMCG Sector

Some of the training programs that are given in the retail sector are:

- Sales Training
- On-the-Job Training
- Seminars/Workshops
- Customer Relationship Management
- Online Course
- Group Study
- Computer-Based Training
- Self-Directed Training

Training & Development in Banking and Insurance Sector

Favorable economic climate and number of other factors such as, growing urbanization, increasing consumerism, rise in the standard of living, increase in financial services for people living in rural areas, etc has increased the demand for wide range of financial products that has led to mutually beneficial growth to the banking sector and economic growth process. This was coincided by technology development in the banking operations. Today most of the Indian cities have networked banking facility as well as Internet banking facility.

In the Insurance sector also, rapid expansion has created about 5 lakh job opportunities approximately in the past five years. These openings are mainly in the field of insurance advisors or marketing agents. The eligibility criteria for these jobs are graduation with some experience in marketing or become insurance agents after completing school but this needs some training.

Earlier there were no training programs as such for insurance agents but on-the-job training only that was given once the new agent was appointed. But now the scenario has changed, with the coming up of big players like ICICI Life Insurance, ICICI Lombard, HDFC Life Insurance, Tata AIG General Insurance etc in this sector, people who have had some formal training are preferred while recruiting because it can be helpful in the insurance field. However, only the insurance degree in this field does not guarantee success. To be successful an agent must have strong interpersonal, networking, and communication skills.

Training and Development in Automobile Sector:

The Indian automobile sector is growing at a rate of about 16% per annum and is now going to be a second fastest growing automobile market in the world. The sector is going through a phase of rapid change and high growth. With the coming up of new projects, the industry is undergoing

technological change. The major players such as, Honda, Toyota, Bajaj, Maruti are now focusing on mass customization, mass production, etc. and are expanding their plants.

According to National Development and Reform Commission (NDRC), India's auto making capacity was 20 million units by the end of the year 2011 exceeding the yearly demand of about 8 million units.

This rapid expansion is because of growing urbanization, rise in the standard of living of consumers, easy availability of finance, liberalization, privatization, and globalization of Indian Industry. This rapid expansion has created lots of job opportunities. Interested one in this sector has to specialize in automobile/mechanical engineering.

Currently, Automobile in India is retaining around 10 million employees and is expected to employ more people in near future. Unorganized sector is employing 67% people while, organized sector is employing only 33% people, which is a major drawback for automobile-sector.

With this rapid expansion and coming up of major players in the sector, the focus is more on the skilled employees and the need of human resource development has increased. The companies are looking for skilled and hard working people who can give their best to the organization. Various companies are opening training institutes to train interested ones in this sector, like Toyota has recently opened Toyota

Technical Training Institute (TTTI) near Bangalore that will offer 4 courses in automobile assembly, mechatronics (a combination of mechanical and industrial electronics), automobile weld and automobile paint. TTTI will provide both a high standard of education and training in automotive technology as well as employment opportunities.

Training and Development in Telecom Sector:

Telecom is one of the fastest growing sectors in India. With increase in competition between the major players like BSNL, MTNL, Hutchison Essar, BPL, Idea, Bharti Tele services, Tata, etc, the requirement for mobile analysts, software engineers, and hardware engineers for mobile handsets has increased. However, holding an engineering degree is not enough to survive in the Telecom Sector. There is constant need of updating of knowledge, skills and attitudes. With this rapid growth in Telecom Sector, the need for trained professionals is bound to rise and so is the training need. The total training market in Telecom Sector is estimated to be Rs 400 crore.

Many top players are spending a huge amount on training and development, for example BSNL alone spends more than 100 crore on training and development of its employees through the Advanced Level Telecommunications Training Centre (ALTTC) and 43 other regional training institutes. Reliance has also established Dhirubhai Ambani Institute of Information and

Communication Technology. In addition to that, Bharti has also tied-up with IIT Delhi for the Bharti School of Telecommunication Technology and Management.

With the increase in competition, availability of huge amount of information through internet, magazines, newspapers, TV, etc, and increased awareness among customers, the demand to impart proper training in non-technological areas like customer care and marketing has increased too. Rapid technological changes, network security threat, mobile application development, growing IP deployment in the sector have brought back the training and development in the priority catalog.

Training and Development in Pharmaceutical Sector:

India Pharmaceutical market is valued at about US \$8 billion and reached to US \$12 billion by 2010. Indian pharmaceutical market is 2% of world's pharmaceutical market. In the last two years, 3900 new generic products have been launched because of which its market value has been increased to about US \$355 million. This rapid growth has also increased the training need of the sector.

- Training Areas
- Brand Protection
- Contamination Control
- Drug Verification
- Supply Chain Visibility
- Recall Management
- Shrinkage Reductions

Preferred Training Methods

Some of the preferred training methods are:

- Web based training
- Class room training
- Workshops
- On-the-job training

Training and Development in Hospitality Sector:

Hospitality sector is growing at a very fast rate in India. The sector is growing at a rate of approximately 8%. This sector can be classified into hotel industry, travel and tourism, restaurants, pubs, clubs and bars, contract catering, and aviation. Other than that, opportunities

also exist in universities, sporting venues, exhibition centers and smaller events management companies.

The major challenge of this sector is shortage of skilled employees along with the challenge of attrition rate. Skilled chefs and managers are in great demand. Managers require huge range of competencies such as, people management, viable skills, business insights, analytic skills, succession planning, and resource development in order to get success in this sector. In addition to that, employees are not enough trained on Business Etiquettes, Courtesy, and Business Communication. Hospitality is all about handling people. So an employee must have right attitude, tolerance, and listening skills in order to move up the hierarchy. There is still a long way to go to inculcate good public relation, interpersonal skills.

With the increase in competition due to the coming up of major players like Four Seasons, Shangri-La, Aman Resorts, etc the need to train employees has increased more than ever before. The major players are now strategizing to increase the turnover of the customers by training their employees on Communication, Dining and Business etiquettes, etc. Some of the essentials required by this sector are:

- Good infrastructure
- Trained trainer
- Quality of content
- Certification of training course
- Effective Training evaluation

Training & Development programs are available for the following areas:

- Food Production
- Food and Beverage Service
- Front Office
- House Keeping

Training and Development in I.T. Industry:

The Indian IT sector is growing at a very fast pace and has generated a revenue of US \$97 billion by 2010. In 2006, it has earned revenue of about US \$ 40 billion with a growth rate of 30%. IT sector had generated 2.3 million jobs by 2010, according to NASSCOM (National Association of Software and Service Companies). With this rapid expansion of IT sector and coming up of major players and new technologies like SAP, the need of human resource development has increased.

There is a direct link between training investment of the companies and the market capitalization. Those companies with higher training investment had higher market capitalization. It clearly indicates that the companies which have successfully implemented training programs have been able to deliver customer goals with effective results. It shows that good training results in enhancement of individual performance, which in turn, helps the organization in achieving its business goals. Training is a tool that can help in gaining competitive advantage in terms of human resource.

With the growing investment by IT companies in the development of their employees many companies have now started their own learning centers. As an example, Sun has its own training department. Accenture has Internet based tool by the name of —My Learning that offers access to its vast learning resources to its employees. Companies are investing in both the technical training, which has always been an essential part in IT industry, as well as in managerial skills development. Companies now keep aside 3-5% of revenue for training programs. As an example, some of the major players like Tata Elexi and Accenture are allocating 7% and 3% respectively of the company's overall revenue.

Training and Development in BPO Industry

The various reasons behind the increasing training need in the BPO SECTOR are:

- BPO industry has generated 1.10 million jobs by 2010, and is expected to generate 6 million jobs by 2015, which is why training need has increased more than ever before.
- High attrition rate in this sector reason being unsatisfied employee, monotonous work, neglected talent, inadequate know-how etc.
- Coming up of high profile BPOs.

People working in BPO sector face the problem of night shift, job stress that results in de motivation. Well designed training program with clear career path increases the job satisfaction among the young professionals and help them in becoming efficient and effective at the work place. Therefore, organizations have to handle such challenges of meeting training needs, although, the sector is taking a lot of initiatives in conducting training for new joiners. Companies are now aligning business goals with training costs. But what is more important is, is the development of the skills of middle management. Various BPO's have an elaborate training infrastructure that includes computer-based Training rooms, and specially trained and qualified in-house trainers. The companies are now busy designing training programs for their employees. These companies try identifying the strengths and weaknesses and are emphasizing more on their personalities, problem-solving.

With constant change in processes, technologies, techniques, methods etc, there is a constant need of updating T&D for the BPO employees to consistently deliver customer goals.

CONCLUSION:

People want value for money that they spend and want great service. If they do not get it, they will not give second chance as they have wide scope. A high quality service depends upon how human resource is trained and developed to handle the competition in the emerging market. It is, therefore imperative to have different methods of training in corporate sectors. This helps employee socialize into their profession via formal and informal process that shapes how they see themselves and how their employers, peers and customers see them. The various corporate sectors in India could shed light on the training & Development atmosphere prevalent in their areas. Training is essential because technology is developing continuously and at a fast rate. Employees have to adapt to technological changes, improve product and service quality and boost productivity to stay in competition. The importance of training as means of improving productivity is readily recognized. Skills required for one job can be transferred to another job; it can be modified and supplemented. Training plays large part in determining the effectiveness and efficiency of the establishment.

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